

Reaction of 4-bromo-2-pyrazolines with fluorene. Part-II. Studies on effect of solvent and base

Arun Ku. Padhy^a, U. Lakshminarayana^b, (Miss) M. Bardhan^c and C. S. Panda^{*c}

^aNational Institute of Science & Technology, Palur Hills, Berhampur, India

^bCollege of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Mohuda, Berhampur-760 002, India

^cSynthetic Organic Laboratory, P. G. Department of Chemistry, Berhampur University, Berhampur-760 007, India

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The reaction of 4-bromo-2-arylpyrazolines with fluorene has been studied in different solvents and employing different bases. The exclusive formation of the 9,9'-disubstituted-fluorene is found to be dependent upon the nature of the solvent and the nature of the base employed as well.

1,3,5-Triaryl-4-bromo-2-pyrazolines can be prepared conveniently and its reaction with fluorene carbanion (generated *in situ*) to produce 9,9'-di(1,3,5-triaryl-4-bromo-2-pyrazolyl)fluorene was reported earlier¹. In continuation of this, we have studied the same reaction in different solvents of varying polarity and employing different bases to generate the fluorene carbanion *in situ*. It was suggested that 9-monosubstituted-fluorene is more acidic than 9-C-H unsubstituted-fluorene^{2,3}. However, it has been observed that solvent as well as the base play a major role in deciding the formation of a particular product.

Results and Discussion

1,3,5-Triaryl-4-bromo-2-pyrazolines was prepared⁴ conveniently and made to react with fluorene carbanion¹ (generated *in situ*) in different solvents like acetic acid, benzene, hexane, tetrahydrofuran and DMSO (in a wide range of solvent polarity). The generation of the fluorene carbanion was carried out employing different bases like NaOH, NaOAc, diphenylamine, Na metal and urotropine (in a wide range of pK_b values). It has been observed that the formation of products, i.e. unreacted fluorene, 9-monosubstituted-fluorene and 9,9'-disubstituted-fluorene, not only depends on the solvent employed⁵ but also on the base employed⁶ for the generation of the carbanion. The solvents and bases employed and the generation of the products in each case is shown in Table 1.

The formation of a single product or a mixture of products was concluded from the melting point data for the same sequence of substrates as reported earlier¹. The mixture thus formed was subjected to chromatography and different substrates were collected and analysed. The percentage of the products formed are within the range of $\pm 5\%$.

Table 1. Percentage of different products formed

Solvent	Base	Unreact. %	Mono- subst. %	Disubst. %	M.p. °C (exp)
Benzene	NaOH	0	0	65	94
Benzene	Diphenyl- amine	0	54	38	82
Acetic acid	NaOAc	0	0	68	99
Hexane	Diphenyl- amine	5	56	34	58
Hexane	Na metal	0	68	5	112
THF	Na metal	0	0	62	96
THF	Diphenyl- amine	2	64	28	75
THF	Urotropine	0	0	46	98
DMSO	Na metal	0	0	58	94

Although it has been observed that in most of the cases the disubstituted product is formed as indicated earlier¹, however, in some cases a mixture of unreacted fluorene, monosubstituted fluorene and disubstituted fluorene derivatives were formed. The explanation for them lies on the two factors, viz. (i) nature of the solvent and (ii) the nature of the base employed.

In non-polar and non-ionising solvents such as hexane, the alkali metal salts possess closely associated cations and anions having a considerable amount of covalent character in the metal-carbon bond. The reaction of the organic halide in hexane occurs by attack at the surface of the insoluble and suspended solid. The monosubstituted fluorene as soon as it is formed, can escape from the surface of the solid into the solution. However, if the newly formed 9-monosubsti-

tuted-fluorene possesses an acidic hydrogen, there will occur on the surface of the solid a reaction as shown below :

Between this product and more of the salt, the extent of which depends upon the acidity of the monosubstituted fluorene. This would lead to disubstitution after further reaction with the alkyl halide. The small amount of disubstituted fluorene actually observed in hexane arose no doubt due to the ionic character of the M-C bond.

When diphenylamine is the base, both the mono- and di-substituted products are formed, the later in a very poor yield. This can be explained on the basis of the nature of the base. The generation of the carbanion from the monosubstituted product is hindered due to steric reasons.

For polar solvents the easeness of the solubility leads to the formation of the disubstituted product preferentially⁵. From the experimental observation we conclude that as reported earlier for certain solvent and bases, the formation of disubstituted product is not possible or else leads to very low yield. The formation of disubstituted product exclusively is completely dependant upon the (i) solvent employed, (ii) strength of the base and (iii) steric reasons, as it is not only kinetically but also thermodynamically controlled.

A close examination of ¹H nmr spectra of these compounds reveals the presence of singlet around δ 4.5–5.0 indicating the presence of Ar-CH system in addition to the multiplet observed at δ 7.0–8.0 due to the bulk aromatic protons for the disubstituted products. The fine splitting shows five different sets of aromatic protons around δ 6.8, 7.2–7.4, 7.4–7.6, 7.8 and 7.9–8.0 respectively⁷. However,

where a mixture of mono- and di-substituted products were formed an additional weak doublet is observed in high resolution at δ 3.5 corresponding to that of 9-CH proton of the monosubstituted fluorene derivative^{8,9}.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were determined on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Column chromatography was carried out on silica gel using ethyl acetate-benzene as elutant.

*1,3,5-Trisubstituted-4-bromo-2-pyrazolines*¹ : To a refluxing solution of 1,3-diaryl-2,3-dibromo-1-propanone (0.03 mol) in absolute ethanol (160 ml) or ethanol-benzene mixture (2 : 1; 240 ml), was added hydrazine hydrate (85%) and substituted hydrazine (0.03 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h on a steam-bath. The solution was then kept cooled at 0° overnight. The separated solid was crystallised from ethanol to afford the products (50–90%).

Reaction of substituted-4-bromopyrazolines with fluorene carbanion : To a stirred suspension of the base in appropriate solvent, fluorene (0.166 g, 0.001 mol) was added and agitated. The 4-bromopyrazoline (0.001 mol) was added to the mixture and stirred for additional 2–3 h. The precipitated solid was filtered out. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure, excess water added and subsequently acidified. The resulting solid products were washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol.

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